

The study of the Northern Thai dialect:
Phonetic variations of Sao Wa sub-variant in Chiang Rai province

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1. Abstract

This paper examines the phonetic differences between the Sao Wa sub-subdialect and the standard Chiang Rai subdialect of the Northern Thai dialect, based on the author's personal experience as a member of the speech community. The variation occurs due to geographical and historical factors. The analysis indicates that the Sao Wa sub-subdialect exhibits tendencies to lengthen vowels and alter pitch patterns in markers, resulting in distinct pronunciation and connotations compared to the standard Chiang Rai dialect. This study enhances our understanding of lesser-known subdialects within the Northern Thai dialect and provides insights into the sociolinguistic dynamics of language variation in the region.

2. Introduction

The Northern Thai dialect, also known as Lanna or Kham Mueang, is a dialect spoken in Northern Thailand, particularly in the provinces of Chiang Mai, Chiang Rai, Lamphun, and Lamphun. It is a member of the Tai-Kadai language family and is closely related to the Lao language (Phongphit 2015). Language variation in the Northern Thai dialect is not random, but rather systematic and patterned, as found in variationist sociolinguistics research (Bayley, Cameron & Lucas 2019). Historically and geographically, each region in Thailand, like the north and the south, used to be independent before being merged together to become Thailand nowadays (Chaiyanara 2016). Different regions may have distinct dialects or pronunciations, which are specific forms of a language associated with a particular geographical area (Mullany 2007). This phenomenon is also found in the Northern Thai dialect (Abramson 1962; Enfield 2003; Sidwell 2009).

Kham Mueang means the language of the principalities (as opposed to the languages of many hill tribe peoples in the surrounding mountainous areas) (“Lan Na” 2022). The Northern Thai dialect or Kham Muang comprises varieties of mutually intelligible subdialects and sub-subdialects (Katsura 1969). Figure 1 and 2 show the complexity of the sub-subdialects within the Northern Thai dialect and where the Sao Wa variant is geographically and linguistically located.

Figure 1 (left): Sao Wa Village (red pin) on the map of Thailand

Figure 2 (right): The chart of Sao Wa variant under the Chiang Rai sub-dialect and the Northern Thai dialect

The most commonly spoken variant in Chiang Rai province is referred to as the standard Chiang Rai subdialect because it is within a subset of the Northern Thai dialect, while the variant spoken in Sao Wa village will be referred to as the Sao Wa sub-subdialect as it is a part of the Chiang Rai subdialect. This article will analyze the phonetic variations of the Sao Wa sub-subdialect and compare them to the standard Chiang Rai subdialect.

Sao Wa is a small village in Bun Rueng sub-district, Chiang Khong district, Chiang Rai province. The inhabitants of Sao Wa village migrated from a village with the same name in Nan province around the year 1882 due to high population density and famine (“The History of Sao Wa Village” 2016). The unfamiliar accent of Sao Wa village compared to neighboring villages is thought to be attributable to this factor.

The family of the author lives in Bun Rueng Tai village where the author's aunt, referred to as Ka, was born and grew up. Because of her marriage, she had to relocate to Sao Wa village to live with her husband's family. As time passed by, Ka started to develop and speak Sao Wa accent unlike other siblings who continued to live in Bun Rueng Tai village and speak the standard Chiang Rai dialect. This fact made this topic even more intriguing from the sociolinguistics angle because Ka spent her childhood years in Bun Rueng Tai village, yet she fully adopted the Sao Wa accent after moving there.

To make the comparison more reliable, one of Ka's siblings, Na, is selected as an informant who represents the standard Chiang Rai sub-dialect because Na shares the same demographic with Ka: age, gender, and education.

This study is the first of its kind to explore the Sao Wa variant within the Chiang Rai subdialect in hope to contribute to the research on the Northern Thai dialect, particularly the less-known subdialects. The analysis is based on the author's first-hand experience as a member of the speech community.

3. Background Theories

Thai Lanna is one of the Tai Yuan ethnic groups. Tai Yuan language is in the Southwestern Tai branch of Tai-Kadai language family (Li 1959). Tai Yuan is also known as Northern Thai dialect, Lanna dialect, or Kham Muang (Zirivarnphicha and Burusphat 2017). In this study, tones of Tai Yuan language will be used as a demonstration of a phonetic shift. Note that the variations are pitches because they do not differentiate the meanings of the words.

Tones in Tai Yuan are analyzed and categorized by Zirivarnphicha and Burusphat (2017) (Table 1). In their work, *The Phonology of Tai Yuan in Thailand*, Zirivarnphicha and Burusphat adapts Gedney's tone box (1972) together with a list of similar sounding words and sounding pairs from the work of Kanlaya (1990) (Ekaphon 2007) and analogous set list developed by Pinrat (2012) that was inspired by the work of Kanlaya (1990) and Pinrat (2003).

Original Syllable/ Original Front Consonant	Normal Syllable			Dead Syllable	
	A without tone marks	B with high tone mark (mai ek)	C with rising tone mark (mai tho)	DL normal syllable with a long vowel	DS dead syllable with a short vowel
Group 1 Voiceless Fricative	A1 หู /hu:/ 'ear' ขา /ka:/ 'leg' หาง /ha:ŋ/ 'tail'	B1 ไผ่ /pai/ 'bamboo/ ข่า /ka:/ 'galangal' ผ่า /pa:/ 'split'	C1 ข้าว /ka:w/ 'rice' เสื้อ /sra:/ 'shirt' ถ้วย /tuai/ 'cup'	DL1 ขวด /kwuad/ 'bottle' หมาก /ma:k/ 'betel' สาก /sa:k/ 'rough'	DS1 หมัด /mad/ 'punch' ผัก /fak/ 'pod' ผัก /pak/ 'vegetable'
Group 2 Voiceless Unaspirated Stop	A2 ปู /pu:/ 'crab' ตา /ta:/ 'eyes' ตีน /ti:n/ 'feet'	B2 ป่า /pa:/ 'forest' ไก่ /gai/ 'chicken' ถั่ว /tua:/ 'bean'	C2 ก้าน /ka:n/ 'stem' กุ้ง /kun/ 'shrimp' ก้าง /ka:ŋ/ 'fish bone'	DL2 ปอด /pɔ:t/ 'lung' ปีก /pi:k/ 'wing' ปาก /pa:k/ 'mouth'	DS2 กบ /gob/ 'frog' ตับ /tab/ 'liver' เป็ด /ped/ 'duck'

Group 3 Glottal	A3 แสง /sɛ:ŋ/ 'light' ดาว /da:w/ 'star' ใบ /bai/ 'leaf'	B3 บ่า /ba:/ 'shoulder' อ่าน /ʔa:n/ 'read' โถง /ʔo:ŋ/ 'jar'	C3 บุง /buŋ/ 'morning glory' อ้อย /ʔo:j/ 'sugar crane' ด้าย /dai:/ 'thread'	DL3 แดด /dɛ:d/ 'sunlight' ดาบ /da:b/ 'sword' ดอก /do:k/ 'flower'	DS3 เบ็ด /bed/ 'hook' ดิบ /dib/ 'raw' อก /ʔo:k/ 'chest'
Group 4 Voiced	A4 มือ /mɔ:/ 'hand' ควาย /kwai:/ 'buffalo' นา /na:/ 'rice field'	B4 นั่ง /nan/ 'sit' น่อง /no:ŋ/ 'calf' ไร่ /rai/ 'land'	C4 น้ำ /nam/ 'water' ลิ้น /lin/ 'tongue' ม้า /ma:/ 'horse'	DL4 ราก /ra:k/ 'root' ลูก /lu:k/ 'child' เลือด /lɛo:d/ 'blood'	DS4 นก /nok/ 'bird' มด /mod/ 'ant' เล็บ /leb/ 'nail'

Table 1: The tonal box demonstrating a sample list of words adapted from Gedney (1972)

It was found that the tones in group A are separated into two categories, namely 1, 2 and 3, 4 (light blue and dark blue background, respectively). Groups B, C, DL, and DS are split into 1, 2, 3 and 4 (light green and dark green background, respectively). Moreover, groups B and DL always have the same tone, similar to C and DS (red and purple cell border, respectively). This results in a total of 6 tones in Northern Thai dialect as in Table 2.

	A	B	C	DL	DS
1	Tone 1	Tone 3	Tone 5	Tone 3	Tone 5
2					
3	Tone 2	Tone 4	Tone 6	Tone 4	Tone 6
4					

Table 2: Tones in Tai Yuan

Apart from the tone specified in the tone box of Zirivarnphicha and Burusphat (2017), another variation is identified. This pitch in the Northern Thai dialect is similar to the mid tone in standard Thai; for example, *ป่า* /pa:/ 'forest', *ผ่า* /p^ha:/ 'split', and *ข่า* /k^ha:/ 'galangal'. In the Northern Thai dialect, however, this tone does not exist. It is rather the pronunciation of pitch. The example words are *จ๊ะ* /tɛa/ (Example 2.2.), *หน่อจ๊ะ* /lɛ/ (Example 3.2.), and *น๊ะ* /na/ (Example 4.1.), and *ก๋า* /ka:/ (Example 6.2.). These words function as a marker. In this study, this pitch is marked with number 7.

4. Literature Review

From the observations of studies related to the Northern Thai dialects, it was found that these dialects have been studied in various scales, ranging from single province studies to comparisons with standard Thai, with only a few studies including sociolinguistic aspects. For example, Wipawan Thinchana (2016) analyzes the variations within Phrae province. One interesting finding is that one of the informants has a tonal variation because the informant regularly communicates with people from outside of the community who come to a hospital. Wipawan also found that age plays an important role, with informants over 50 years old retaining the original tonal characteristics in their pronunciation, as Wipawan expected the shift to be more prominent in the younger generation. In addition, the pronunciation remains the same due to the prestige of the Phrae dialect as a lingua franca among various groups of people in Phrae province.

An example of work conducted on the Northern Thai dialects in many provinces is the work of Mayuree Poopholwattanaporn (2016). Mayuree studies the Northern Thai dialect at Baan Huay Muang, Thasailuat Sub-district, Maesod District, Tak Province, and compares the findings with several variants of the Northern Thai dialect, such as Nan, Phrae, and Chiang Mai. In Mayuree's studies, the Northern Thai dialect found in provinces outside of the northern regions is also taken into account, such as in Nakhon Ratchasima in the northeastern region, as well as in Saraburi, Ratchaburi, and Nakhon Pathom in the central region.

Lastly, Katsura (1969) investigated the phonology of the four sub-variants of the Northern Thai dialects in Chiang Rai, Chiang Mai, Lampang, and Phrae, and compared them with standard Thai in Bangkok. In Katsura's study, it has been found that among the four northern dialects, the Chiang Mai variation is the most similar to standard Thai. Within Chiang Mai province, Katsura also found that the variations in the remote districts are more similar to the other three northern sub-dialects.

The studies of Wipawan, Mayuree, and Katsura focus on the Northern Thai dialects in single or different provinces, not on variations within the same dialect. Although Katsura's conclusion mentions the differences between the variations of the Chiang Mai sub-dialect spoken in central and rural districts, it does not contain details of the non-standard Chiang Mai dialects.

5. Data and Methods

This study employs a non-probability purposive sampling method. For the Sao Wa variation, data is collected from Ka, along with two other informants who live in Sao Wa village. For the standard Chiang Rai dialect, data is collected from Na's speech and two other informants who live in Bun Rueng

Tai village. To align with Ka and Na's demographics, the informants must be females over 50 years old who have not completed compulsory education.

Demography / Dialect		Sao Wa	Standard Chiang Rai
Age and Education	above 50 without compulsory education	3	3

Table 1: The distribution of the number of informants based on age and education

To ensure data standardization, consistency across participants, and comparability of results, scripted data is used. Informants are provided with a list of sentences to speak in Chiang Rai dialect three times per sentence. The sentences are then transcribed in IPA and compared for phonetic differences at the lexeme level. Tone numbers 1-6 are placed next to the transcription, following the tone box used in the study of Zirivarnphicha and Burusphat (2017).

The list of sentences are as follows:

- ตั่วจะไปกะ “Do you want to go?”
- ตั่วยังมาจะอันนะ “How come you did that?”
- ป่าไปปละ “I am (aunt) not going.”

6. Results

The phonetic variations in Sao Wa sub-subdialect mainly occur in the markers. The deviations of Sao Wa sub-subdialect found in this study are that it tends to prolong the vowels and change the pitch of the markers. The list of sentences with tone numbers are illustrated below.

(1.1.) Standard Chiang Rai ตั่ว จะ ไป กะ
 /tua:/ /tea/ /pai/ /ka5/
 You will go Q
 ‘Do you want to go?’

(1.2.) Sao Wa ตั่ว จะ ไป ก้า
 /tua:/ /tea/ /pai/ /ka::1/
 You will go Q
 ‘Do you want to go?’

(2.1.) Standard Chiang Rai ตั่ว หยั่ง มา ยะ **จะอัน** นะ
 /tua:/ /ɲaŋ/ /ma:/ /ɲa/ /**tca6**·ʔan/ /na/
 You why come do that Q
 ‘How come you did that?’

(2.2.) Sao Wa ตั่ว หยั่ง มา ยะ **จะอัน** นะ
 /tua:/ /ɲaŋ/ /ma:/ /ɲa/ /**tca7**·ʔan/ /na/
 You why come do that Q
 ‘How come you did that?’

(3.1.) Standard Chiang Rai ป้า ึ๋ ไป **และ**
 /pa:/ /bɔ:/ /pai/ /**le6**/
 Aunt-1SG NEG go NEG
 ‘I am (aunt) not going.’

(3.2.) Sao Wa ป้า ึ๋ ไป **แหละ**
 /pa:/ /bɔ:/ /pai/ /**le7**/
 Aunt-1SG NEG go NEG
 ‘I am (aunt) not going.’

Sao Wa variant demonstrates several aspects of deviation from the standard Chiang Rai variant. The main difference is that the variation tends to prolong the vowels of question markers placed at the end of the sentences (example 1.1. and 1.2.). In addition, there is a phonetic shift from tone 6 to pitch 7 (example 2.1., 2.2., 3.1., and 3.2.).

Although the previous deviations do not change the meanings of the sentences, there are many pitches in standard Chiang Rai dialect, as well as in Sao Wa sub-subdialect that convey different connotations or have different functions. Some pitches are unique to the Sao Wa variant. This topic may not be directly related to the deviations of Sao Wa sub-subdialect from standard Chiang Rai sub dialect, but it is worth mentioning because, similar to the previous examples, the variations in the following examples occur in markers, and these examples further reflect the varieties between and within both dialects, which leads to a more well-rounded understanding of the complexity and how the phonetic variations function in these dialects.

In Example 2, the ending *นะ* /na/ can be pronounced in different pitches in standard Chiang Rai dialect. The pitch of *นะ* /na7/ in Example 2 conveys a normal level of criticism, while when the pitch changes to *นะ* /na5/ as in Example 4.2. below, it intensifies the meaning of criticism accompanying the connotation of questioning.

(4.1.) *ตัว* *ยัง* *มา* *ะ* *จะอื่น* ***นะ***
 /tua:/ /jaŋ/ /ma:/ /ja/ /tɕaːʔan/ /na7/
 You why come do that Q
 ‘How come you did that?’

(4.2.) *ตัว* *ยัง* *มา* *ะ* *จะอื่น* ***นะ***
 /tua:/ /jaŋ/ /ma:/ /ja/ /tɕaːʔan/ /na5/
 You why come do that Q
 ‘How come you did that?’

Example 5 below shows that different tones signify different meanings. In Example 5.1., *แต่* /tɛ4/ marks a question while *แต่* /tɛ6/ in Example 5.2. means ‘true’ or ‘real’, and consequently, the question marker in Example 5.2. falls to *ไหนะ* /nɔ/.

(5.1.) *ตัว* *ะ* ***แต่***
 /tua:/ /ja/ /tɛː4/
 you do Q
 ‘Did you do it?’

(5.2.) *ตัว* *ะ* ***แต่*** *ไหนะ*
 you do real Q
 /tua:/ /ja/ /tɛː6/ /nɔ/
 ‘Did you really do it?’

Examples 4 and 5 demonstrate phonetic variations in standard Chiang Rai dialect. In the following examples, apart from the phonetic variations in standard Chiang Rai dialect, the phonetic variations in Sao Wa sub-subdialect are also present.

Example 6 shows different pitches of the suggestive/instructive marker *กั๋* /ka/. Compared to Example 6.1., Example 6.2. prolongs the vowel while maintaining the same tone signaling more intimacy and less hierarchy between speaker and addressee. The connotation also becomes more suggestive than instructive. Example 6.3. has a gliding pitch in a single syllable from *กั๋* /ka::1/ to *กั๋* /ka::6/ with an extra long vowel. This even softens the meaning of suggestion and conveys the connotation of politeness and concern. Variations in Examples 6.1.-6.3. are found in both standard Chiang Rai dialect and Sao Wa variant, but Example 6.2. are more common in the Sao Wa variant.

(6.1.) *ตั๋* *จะไป* *ยะ* *จะอั้น* *กั๋*
 /tua:/ /tea·pai/ /ɲa/ /tea·ʔan/ /ka7/
 you NEG do that SUG (suggestive marker)
 ‘Don’t do that.’

(6.2.) *ตั๋* *จะไป* *ยะ* *จะอั้น* *กั๋*
 /tua:/ /tea·pai/ /ɲa/ /tea·ʔan/ /ka:7/
 you NEG do that SUG (suggestive marker)
 ‘Don’t do that.’

(6.3.) *ตั๋* *จะไป* *ยะ* *จะอั้น* *กั๋-กั๋*
 /tua:/ /tea·pai/ /ɲa/ /tea·ʔan/ /ka::1-6/
 you NEG do that SUG (suggestive marker)
 ‘Please, don’t do that.’

The same observation of the suggestive/instructive marker *กั๋* /ka/ is found in Example 7 below.

(7.1.) *จะไป* *นอน* *ดึก* *กั๋*
 /tea·pai/ /nɔ:n/ /dɯk/ /ka7/
 NEG sleep late SUG (suggestive marker)
 ‘Don’t sleep late.’

(7.2.) *จะไป* *นอน* *ดึก* *กั๋*
 /tea·pai/ /nɔ:n/ /dɯk/ /ka:7/
 NEG sleep late SUG (suggestive marker)

‘Don’t sleep late.’

(7.3.)	จะไป	นอน	ดึก	กำ-กำ
	/tea:pai/	/nɔ:n/	/dɯk/	/ka:1-6/
	NEG	sleep	late	SUG (suggestive marker)
	‘Please, don’t sleep late.’			

7. Summary and Discussions

This study shows that geographical and historical factors contribute to the variations in dialects. The pronunciation of Sao Wa sub-subdialect is different from standard Chiang Rai subdialect in that it tends to prolong the vowels and change the pitches of the markers. When considering both Sao Wa variant and standard Chiang Rai subdialect, while most phonetic variations do not change the meanings of the word, some lead to changes in connotations.

To further elaborate on this study, the phonetics analysis programs like PRAAT or CECIL could be employed, and more examples should be included to make the analysis more systematic, robust, and statistical. Moreover, as mentioned in the introduction about the origin of Sao Wa habitants, the similarity of the pronunciation between Sao Wa villagers in Chiang Rai and in Nan province should be examined to find out if there are similar characteristics in pronunciation pertaining between the two places. In addition, the study would be more multifaceted if it includes the informants with different ages and education levels.

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Consent to Participate in a Research Project

Affiliation

Linguistic Diversity and Digital Humanity Programme, Faculty of Arts, University of Helsinki

The study topic

The study of the Northern Thai dialect: Tones of Sao Wa sub-variant in Chiang Rai province

Purpose of the study

To compare the Sao Wa variation with the standard Chiang Rai dialect

Consent statement

I, hereby, consent to the use of my recordings as a part of the above-mentioned research.

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Name

.....

Signature

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Date and place